

Conditional Probability and Time in Quantum Bound States

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We argue that in a quantum bound state with one particle, the particle receives stochastic hits from a potential. As a result, if one examines a point x , the particle may be present at t_i with momentum p_i (in both the forward and backward directions) leading to a momentum distribution with a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Thus, one does not follow a stochastic particle in time, but rather describes it by a probability distribution at each x . One may next ask whether this conditional probability at x changes in time? This is not the actual time related to stochastic motion of the particle. To answer this question, we argue one must consider interactions which occur at x which are part of an energy equation. Even in classical physics, the energy equation at x indicates how a particle's motion changes. Thus, we argue one does not simply take measurements at x of t_i and p_i , but that at each t_i , a particle with p_i is undergoing dynamic changes and these may be considered as well. If one describes the quantum picture by $W(x)$ i.e. a momentum distribution, one may find a collective interaction given by $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + VW$.

The coupling between $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ and the particle conditional probabilities in W is apparent in the VW term. This energy term should describe whether the momentum distribution changes in time i.e. should be proportional to dW/dt (partial derivative), but should also equal the average energy. Thus, a link exists between ensemble energy and time. In this note, we argue that these ideas may be applied to $P(p/x)$ in a bound state resonance because the same E applies to each p .

Conditional Probability of a Stochastic Particle

We argue that in quantum mechanics, stochastic motion of a particle (due to stochastic hits from a potential) is replaced with a conditional momentum probability distribution (including forward and backward motion) at each x : $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ (which we try to derive). One may wonder what use one may make of $P(p/x)$, but it seems it yields an energy conservation equation i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\left[\text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

We argue $P(p/x)$ follows from expressing a potential as $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. This unusual form seems to follow physically from the behaviour of virtual photons. Each $V(k)$ yields a momentum k hit although modified by $\exp(ikx)$. Thus, the quantum particle undergoes stochastic hits and a probability distribution at each x is established. To find this distribution (rather than follow the stochastic particle in time), one may argue that each $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ term couples with a $p-k$ momentum with probability $P((p-k)/x)$ to form a p momentum particle at x . Then:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) + \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx) P((p-k)/x) = E P(p/x) \quad ((2))$$

Next, consider $x \rightarrow x+b$, where b is tiny, to obtain the coefficient of b :

$$[E - p^2/2m] dP(p/x)/dx / P(p/x) + \text{Sum over } k V(x)\exp(ikx) \{ k + dP(p-k)/dx / P(p-k/x) \} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

A solution of ((3)) is: $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a normalization constant (function). As a result, there exists a solution in which $P(p/x)$ changes in space in the same unusual manner as $V(k)\exp(ikx)$. For an equilibrium solution, one does not expect $P(p/x)$ to change with time, but how does one show this formally?

Effect of Time

We have argued that a stochastic potential $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$ creates a momentum conditional probability distribution of $P(p/x)$ at each point. As a result, one may try to measure such a distribution. It may be noted that there is not simply a static distribution $P(p/x)$. Each time a particle with momentum p_i is present at x , it may receive a stochastic hit which changes it to momentum p_j . Thus, one takes measurements to determine the distribution as well as measurements defining its dynamics at the same time. If there is an equilibrium, this should be possible. The interactions the particle undergoes are with the stochastic potential terms $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ which couple with the momentum conditional probabilities or relative probabilities. This yields an energy type of equation i.e.

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + VW \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } VW = \text{Sum over } k, p V(k)\exp(ikx) a(p)\exp(ipx)$$

((4)) should equal average energy, but should also be a measure of how the ensemble $W(x)$ changes in time. Thus, we suggest that:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + VW = b \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) \quad (\text{partial derivative}) = EW \quad ((5)) \quad \text{with } b = i$$

((5)) applies to $W(x,t)$, the complete distribution. What about a specific $P(p/x)$?

If one writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series in the time-independent Schrodinger equation and collects $\exp(ipx)$ terms, then:

$$p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx) + \text{Sum over } k V(k)a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, each p is linked to the same E i.e. there is a resonance. Furthermore, one may write: $E = i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(iEt)$ and assign an oscillating time function $\exp(iEt)$ with each $P(p/x)$ probability, not just with $W(x,t)$.

The time t is associated with $P(p/x,t)$ and $W(x,t)$ and not with the time used to follow physical motion of a quantum bound particle. In classical mechanics, t is the time associated with the actual motion of a particle. Thus, one knows $v(x)$ and $x(t)$ i.e. the trajectory, but in the literature there exist calculations related to a probability density $P(x) = Cdx/|v(x)|$. In fact, this is taken to be equivalent to $W(x)W(x)$ for high energy levels. To see this in a hand-wavy manner, consider that

dx in the classical case is large compared with the quantum case. In quantum mechanics, for large p (momentum), dx must be very small to distinguish different px values. Next, consider that at a particular x , the average kinetic energy is dominated by a p associated with the classical kinetic energy i.e. $WW \text{ approx} = \sin(px)\sin(px)C^*C$. One next needs to scale the quantum dx so it is equivalent to the classical one. This may be done, it seems, by multiplying and dividing by p . At a peak value of $\sin(px)\sin(px)$, one has: $\text{spatial density} = \text{constant} / p$. Thus even in classical physics where one knows the exact trajectory, one may ignore this trajectory and write a $P(x)$ for the probability of the particle to be at x and think of the problem in statistical terms.

It is interesting that ((6)) contains a time change as well as cycling term (second term on LHS) together. The distribution $P(p/x)$ is created by many different $p-k$ values combined with various $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ terms, but at the same time dynamics occur which are linked to E i.e. the energy associated with $P(p/x)$ is related to its change in time.

Issue of Phases

It is interesting that $P(p/x)$ contains two phases $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(iEt)$. The $\exp(ipx)$ phase follows from $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ which in turn follows from the nature of a (virtual) photon. Thus, it seems one argues that the probability of a quantum particle undergoing stochastic hits mimics that of a photon. This is carried over to the case of a quantum particle moving in a vacuum. To see a link between the bound $P(p/x)$ and that of a free particle consider:

$$p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx) + \text{Sum over } k V(k)a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

and divide by $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Then:

$$p^2/2m + \text{Function}(p) = E \quad ((7))$$

In other words, there is no x present in ((7)), it is the equation of a free particle moving through a region with a constant potential $\text{Function}(p)$. Each p has its own constant potential (with a different value). It may be noted that ((7)) was obtained from an equation for $P(p/x)$, so it applies to the conditional probability and not the actual motion of a particle in a bound system. It seems a "free" electron may receive stochastic hits from the vacuum and move with a probability $\exp(ikx)$ where k is the average momentum. (Otherwise, why not treat it classically?) (Others, in the literature, consider $\exp(ikx)$ to be linked to zitterbewegung i.e. an intrinsic internal motion leading to spiral type motion.)

The phase $\exp(ipx)$ causes different $P(p/x)$ to interfere with each other, meaning that conditional averages of p or p^2 at x may receive positive or negative contributions from $P(p/x)+P(-p/x)$. We argue that stochastic motion may lead to $P(p/x)+P(-p/x)$ describing motion opposite to general flow, hence yielding a negative contribution. How may one apply this to two slit or single slit experiments? In such an experiment, the quantum particle interacts with the potential of the slits which is stochastic. In such a case, there is only $P(p/x)$, but it still takes the

form $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ leading to an interference pattern. So we argue that in a bound system, "interference" occurs continually, but a particle may only have one p value at a time, so one considers $P(p/x)$ at different times and calculates an average which considers motion with and against the flow [$\sum \text{over } p \quad pP(p/x)$]

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that time in the Schrodinger equation is associated with not only ensemble time $W(x,t)$, but also with conditional probability $P(p/x,t)$. We argue a quantum particle moves stochastically in time (a different time than that in the Schrodinger equation). One is not interested in the exact motion of the particle in time, but rather in a probability pattern at each x i.e. a conditional momentum distribution. If $V(x)=\sum \text{over } k \quad V(k)\exp(ikx)$, $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ i.e. it follows the virtual photon-like behaviour of the potential. One may measure $P(p/x)$, but at the same time measure its change through interactions with $V(x)$ i.e. $V(x)W$. Such a term, however, is part of an energy equation $EW = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x)$ so we argue EW is proportional to dW/dt (partial derivative). Furthermore, we argue one may write an energy equation for $P(p/x)$ (see ((6))) containing $EP(p/x)$ for all p as there is a resonance. Then $i\frac{d}{dt}P(p/x,t)=EP(p/x,t)$.